

Research Article

Rational Use Of Antibiotics In Super Specialty Settings: Trends And Challenge

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ABSTRACT

Background: Antibiotics usage has increased globally, the antibiotics are frequently prescribed to the patients, and it has been discovered that most of the antibiotics prescribed in healthcare settings are inappropriate. The misuse of these antibiotics leads to the rise of antimicrobial resistance, adverse drug reactions, and higher morbidity including high hospitalization costs.

Objective: This study aims to study the utilization of the antibiotics in super specialty hospital.

Methodology: It is a prospective observational study conducted over period of 3 months where the data of 50 patients hospitalized in the in-patient department were taken. All the data collected were designed in sheets and input in Microsoft Excel and the figures and tables are presented.

Results: Among those 50 patients studied it was found that the patient of age group 21-30 received most antibiotics among all age groups, the most prescribed antibiotic was Amikacin, and the patients were prescribed mostly with the antibiotics of “Orange” category.

Conclusion: Inappropriate antibiotic use is a major global health concern leading to antibiotic resistance and other negative consequences. While antibiotics are effective against bacterial infections, their misuse can lead to the emergence of resistant strains, making infections harder to treat and potentially spreading to others. Therefore, responsible antibiotic use, including proper dosage, duration, and indication, is crucial to combatting antimicrobial resistance and maintaining the effectiveness of these life-saving drugs.

Keywords: Antibiotic utilization, antibiotic resistance, antibiotic stewardship.

INTRODUCTION

Antibiotic utilization refers to the proper use of antibiotics in treating bacterial infections and preventing their spread [1]. It involves prescribing the correct antibiotic, in the right dosage, and for the appropriate duration to ensure effective treatment while minimizing side effects and resistance [2]. Responsible antibiotic use is essential to avoid overuse or misuse, which can lead to antibiotic resistance, making infections harder to treat [3]. Antibiotic stewardship programs and guidelines help promote optimal utilization in healthcare, agriculture, and veterinary settings [4].

Antibiotics have made a huge impact on modern medicines, reducing the morbidity rate to a greater extent [5]. Even though it has been helpful in most treatment, there remains a concern about the misuse and overdose of the antibiotics during the treatment phase [6].

Antibiotic stewardship programme is one that ensures responsible use of the antibiotics [7]. Multidisciplinary teamwork is necessary and helps to make sure the patients receive the appropriate antibiotics, and the proper dose required during treatment duration [8]. Properly managed antibiotic stewardship program (ASP) reduces the rates of resistance, treatment cost and enhances the outcomes [9].

METHODOLOGY

A prospective study was conducted on 50 patients over the period of 3 months on the inpatients of Super-speciality hospital, the hospital had various wards like the intensive care unit (ICU), burn ward, male ward, female ward and orthopaedic ward, all these were considered for study purpose. The data were collected from the patient's case notes, prescriptions, treatment charts and laboratory reports of the patients admitted in the hospital.

RESULTS

After conducting the observational study following data were collected

Table 1: Age wise patient distribution

Sl no	Age group	No. of patients	% of patients
1	0 to 10	4	8%
2	11 to 20	5	10%
3	21 to 30	15	30%
4	31 to 40	6	12%
5	41 to 50	8	16%
6	51 to 60	4	8%
7	61 to 70	2	4%
8	71 to 80	4	8%
9	above 81	2	4%

The patients observed in the study consisted of people from all age group. It included people from 0 to 90 years of age groups. The data mentioned above (Table 1) shows a demographic data of the patients from all the age groups. From the study it was found that the patients from age groups 0-10 was 12.50 %, 11-20 was 10 %, 21 -30 was 30 %, 31-40 was 12 %, 41-50 was 16 %, 51-60 was 8 %, 61-70 was 4 %, 71-80 was 8 % and 81-90 was 4 %.

Table 2: Number of antibiotics used

sl no.	name of antibiotic	no. of antibiotic used	% of antibiotic
1	Amikacin	44	88%
2	Ceftriaxone	33	66%
3	Piperacillin	12	24%
4	Tazobactam	11	22%
5	Clindamycin	10	20%
6	Metronidazole	7	14%
7	Meropenum	4	8%
8	Cefuroxime	4	8%
9	Doxycycline	2	4%
10	Azithomycin	2	4%
11	Cefixime	1	2%
12	Moxifloxacin	1	2%
13	Amoxicillin&clavulanic acid	1	2%

Table 2 shows the demographic data of total number of times the antibiotics have been used among those 50 patients observed in the study. From the study it was found that the antibiotic *amikacin* has been frequently used among the patients.

Table 3. Gender wise patient distribution

Sl no.	Gender	Percentage of Gender
1	Male	94%
2	Female	6%

Table 3 Consists of the demographic data of the patient's distribution according to the gender of the patient.

Table 4. Category of antibiotics used

Category of antibiotics used	No. of Antibiotic used
Red	4
Orange	5
Green	3

Table 4 Consist of the demographic data of the categories of restricted antibiotics used for the patients. From the observation it was found that, most of the patients were provided with 2° (**Orange**) restricted antibiotics and the least used was 1° (**Green**) restricted antibiotics.

Table 5. Percentage of antibiotics used

Sl no.	No. of antibiotics used	Number of patients	% of antibiotic used
1	1	5	10
2	2	32	64
3	3	12	24

Table 5 Consists of the demographic data providing an overview of the antibiotics used according to the category of the restricted antibiotics and the total percentage of the antibiotics used in patients. It also indicates the total number of patients on which the antibiotics were used accordingly.

Table 6. Percentage of antibiotics used per patient

Number of antibiotics per patient	Percentage of antibiotic used
1	10
2	64
3	24

Table No. 6 Consists of the demographic data providing an overview of the percentage of antibiotics used per person according to the data collected. It indicates that most of the patients were administered with two antibiotics with the overall percentage of 64% and the other patients were administered with one and three antibiotics with percentage of 10% and 24% respectively.

DISCUSSION

The utilization of antibiotics is a significant concern, particularly considering the escalating global challenge of antibiotic resistance. Misuse or excessive use of antibiotics, such as administering them for viral infections or for situations where they are unnecessary, fosters the emergence of resistant pathogens, complicating treatment strategies and extending hospitalizations. Keeping track of antibiotic usage through organized protocols guarantees that these medications are prescribed only when essential, at the correct dosage, and for the suitable time frame. A 1996 study indicated that approximately **47.9%** of children aged 0-4 received at least one oral antibiotic prescription. By the year 2000, this figure decreased to **38.1%** [10]. As compared to our study the antibiotics given to the children of 0-10 years of age were about 12.50%. The antibiotic most prescribed to the patients was *Azithromycin* [11] whereas in our study it was found that the most prescribed antibiotic to the children was ceftriaxone. According to a 2016/17 study, antibiotic prescribing rates for adults stood at 89.2 prescriptions per 1,000 registered patients [12], and the most prescribed antibiotics were *Amoxicillin*, *Azithromycin*. In our study it found that the most prescribed antibiotics to the adult patients was *Amikacin* (**88%**). A study on older adults found that 71-year-old individuals had an antibiotic usage rate of 80.3% [13]. Whereas in our study it was found that most of the antibiotics were administered to the adults of age group if 21-30 years. A study published in *BMC Medicine* observed that antibiotic misuse is high in outpatient settings, especially among adults. Among older adults, inappropriate prescribing has been linked to lack of awareness about antibiotic resistance [14] On investigating the patient's cases in our study, the results were like the previous research, there was lack of awareness about the antibiotics resistance among people. Antibiotics consumption has increased with time among the adults in the middle-income countries and high-income countries. [15][16]

CONCLUSION

Inappropriate antibiotic use is a major global health concern leading to antibiotic resistance and other negative consequences. While antibiotics are effective against bacterial infections, their misuse can lead to the emergence of resistant strains, making infections harder to treat and potentially spreading to others. Therefore, responsible antibiotic use, including proper dosage, duration, and indication, is crucial to combatting antimicrobial resistance and maintaining the effectiveness of these life-saving drugs.

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Conflict of interest:

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